

Top Universities in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "QS university ranking average score of top 3 universities" in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) represents a key indicator for assessing the quality and competitiveness of a country's academic institutions. This variable refers to the average scores achieved by the top three universities of a nation in the QS World University Rankings, one of the most recognized and respected global rankings for evaluating higher education quality. The importance of this variable in the GII lies in the strong correlation between academic excellence and a country's ability to innovate. Top-tier universities not only attract both international and local talent, but also serve as centers of advanced research, producing fundamental scientific and technological breakthroughs. Innovation often originates within universities, which foster the development of highly qualified human capital and encourage collaboration among students, researchers, businesses, and other actors within the innovation ecosystem. As a result, a high average score for the top three universities in a nation indicates that the country is well-positioned to stimulate and sustain innovation through research and development. The QS rankings are based on various criteria, including academic reputation, employer reputation, student-to-faculty ratio, citations per faculty member, and the percentage of international students. These factors reflect the universities' ability to attract and train talent, as well as the quality of their scientific output. Overall, the average score of the top three universities in this ranking offers an indirect but significant measure of a country's innovation potential, highlighting the crucial role that elite universities play in creating ecosystems conducive to innovation. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Average score of the top 3 universities in the QS ranking in 2022. The data provided on the average score of the top three universities in the QS ranking for 2022 offers insight into the global distribution of excellence in higher education. Analyzing the scores reveals a clear global hierarchy, with some well-defined trends. The United States leads the ranking with a score of 98.9, closely followed by the United Kingdom with 98.5. This result reflects the international prestige of universities such as Harvard, MIT, and Stanford in the US, and Oxford, Cambridge, and Imperial College London in the UK. These institutions not only attract top academic talent worldwide but also benefit from significant research funding and advanced infrastructures that promote innovation. Their top positions highlight the historic and ongoing role of these two countries in providing world-class education and leading global research. China, in third place with a score of 86.8, demonstrates the rapid rise of its universities in global rankings. Institutions such as Tsinghua and Peking University have seen steady growth thanks to substantial government investments in research and education, signaling China's ambition to emerge as a global leader in innovation and technology. Switzerland and Hong Kong follow with scores above 80. Switzerland, home to institutions like ETH Zurich and EPFL, stands out for its strong focus on science and innovation. Similarly, Hong Kong, with universities such as the University of Hong Kong (HKU) and the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST), establishes itself as a key Asian educational hub, with international collaborations and high research productivity. Canada, Australia, and Japan, also with scores above 80, demonstrate a consistent commitment to high-quality higher education and research. These countries have long academic traditions and promote advanced research environments, contributing to their prominent positions. Countries such as South Korea, France, and Germany, with scores between 70 and 75, while having advanced educational systems, rank slightly behind global leaders. Their universities are highly respected locally but may have lower international visibility or fewer institutions among

the world's top-ranked, despite their significant national impact. In the mid-range, Singapore (69.4), the Netherlands, and Sweden hold strong positions, thanks to universities that are heavily oriented towards research and innovation. Countries like Italy (49.1) and Malaysia (58) show solid educational systems but with a limited number of internationally renowned universities. In the lower ranks, countries like Kazakhstan, Thailand, and Colombia reflect regions where higher education systems are still developing or less recognized internationally. These countries may have good domestic educational systems but face challenges in gaining global visibility due to limited research funding or less frequent international collaborations. At the bottom of the ranking, countries like Iraq, Panama, and Croatia, with scores below 5, face significant challenges in their higher education systems, related to political instability, lack of investment, or poor integration into international educational networks. In summary, the data reveals a global hierarchy in higher education, with historically dominant Western countries maintaining top positions, while emerging economies like China and Singapore are rapidly gaining ground. Conversely, many developing nations still face considerable challenges in establishing themselves on the global educational stage, although there are signs of regional progress.

Average score of the top 3 universities in the QS ranking between 2013 and 2022. The reported data highlights the evolution of the average score of the top three universities from various countries in the QS ranking between 2013 and 2022. This comparison reveals significant changes in the global higher education landscape, with some countries showing marked improvements while others have experienced a decline. Among the countries with the most notable improvement, Belarus and Estonia stand out with an increase of over 100%. Specifically, Belarus raised its score by 8.9 points (a 115.58% increase), followed by Estonia with an increase of 8.7 points (106.1%). This improvement can be attributed to increased investments in higher education and research infrastructure. Gulf countries like Bahrain, Iran, and Qatar have also shown significant growth, with respective increases of 90.16%, 89.71%, and 83.78%. These results reflect the strong commitment of these nations to improving their universities through modernization and internationalization programs. Other countries, such as Pakistan and Malaysia, have seen improvements in the average score of their top three universities, with increases of 37.85% and 31.22%, respectively. Malaysia, in particular, has undertaken strategic reforms and investments to attract international students and improve research quality, contributing to its significant progress. On the other hand, some countries have shown a decline in their universities' scores. For instance, Ireland recorded a reduction of 20.27%, with a drop of 12.2 points, while South Africa experienced a similar decline (-20.51%). This drop could reflect economic challenges or reduced investment in higher education in these countries. Notably, countries like Israel, once a leader in research and innovation, suffered a significant decrease of 25.05%, losing 12.8 points. This result is surprising, given Israel's reputation for academic and technological excellence, but it may indicate increasing global competition. Other countries that experienced notable declines include Canada (-4.76%), Germany (-3.6%), the Netherlands (-3.27%), and Australia (-2.5%). Despite these reductions, it is important to note that the average scores of these countries remain very high, indicating that their universities continue to be globally competitive, though they may be feeling the pressure from emerging institutions.

Conclusions. On average, the value of the average score of the top 3 universities in the QS ranking between 2013 and 2022 increased by 1.35%, rising from 41.77 points to 42.33 points. The top performers are: Belarus with +115.58%, Estonia with +106.10%, Bahrain with +90.16%, Iran with +89.71%, and Qatar with +83.78%. The worst performers are: Ireland with -20.27%, South Africa with -20.51%, the Philippines with -23.4%, Egypt with -23.85%, and Israel with -25.05%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Belarus	7,7	16,6	8,9	115,58
	Estonia	8,2	16,9	8,7	106,1
	Bahrain	6,1	11,6	5,5	90,16
	Iran, Islamic Rep.	13,6	25,8	12,2	89,71
	Qatar	7,4	13,6	6,2	83,78
Worse Performers	Ireland	60,2	48	-12,2	-20,27
	South Africa	39,5	31,4	-8,1	-20,51
	Philippines	26,5	20,3	-6,2	-23,4
	Egypt, Arab Rep.	26	19,8	-6,2	-23,85
	Israel	51,1	38,3	-12,8	-25,05

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